

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the activity monitoring and behavior tracking infrastructure developed within the AgeingAtWork platform, towards collecting a rich set of data, which can be used to build a variety of personalized interventions and tools for pervasive health monitoring. The developed modular infrastructure enables the collection of multimodal data including activity and sleep information from wearable devices, smartphones, and third-party apps, keystroke typing data, location information, data from medical and environmental IoT devices, as well as self-reports. The central piece of the architecture is the abstraction middleware, which handles and communicates with the built-in modalities and retrieves or stores information from/to the external components, such as the workers Virtual User Model database. All the individual modalities were built as add-on libraries, while also the communication with the external components is based on Rest-Full logic, offering extensibility, interoperability and ease of maintenance. Use case studies are demonstrated, aiming to show the value and applicability of the infrastructure in developing different digital health monitoring tools and interventions. More specifically, a Virtual Coaching component was integrated, capable of providing useful interventions in real-world settings, with the aim to improve worker's general health and workability. Furthermore, a Healthcare Platform (Dashboard) was integrated enabling workers to overview their collected behavioral data and enhance their self-awareness.

In conclusion, the developed multimodal framework brings useful insights into the design of modular and extensible infrastructures for behavior and activity tracking and provides the basis upon which useful health monitoring tools and interventions can be built.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AOSP	Android Open-Source Project
API	Application Programming Interface
CNN	Convolution Neural Network
DTW	Dynamic Time Warping
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAR	Human Activity Recognition
HL7	Health Level Seven
HMM	Hidden Markov Model
IOT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MDD	Major Depressive Disorder
POI	Points of Interest
SDK	Software Development Kit
SHA	Secure Hash Algorithm
VUM	Virtual User Model

Table 1. Definitions

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable presents the multimodal framework that will support the collection of all data required for the AgeingAtWork platform, which is first and foremost needed towards building digital health tools and interventions for the ageing workers. We present the rationale of the developed modular framework, along with its architectural elements, towards the unobtrusive activity and behavior tracking of workers. The framework captures a very rich set of data sources enabling the collection of activity information from wearable devices, smartphones, and third-party apps, keystroke typing data, location information, data from medical and environmental IoT devices, and self-reports. Furthermore, proof-of-concept case studies based on the developed framework are demonstrated to show the potential of developing different digital health interventions for ageing workers.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

This deliverable is mainly part of Task 4.1 – Open and extensive framework for the worker tracking infrastructure, with the purpose to build a modular and extensible technical infrastructure, based on which different digital tools and interventions can be built. In this context, the deliverable is also related to Task 4.2 – Unobtrusive worker activity and behavior monitoring, in which the detection of activities and behaviors of the workers takes place through the developed multimodal infrastructure, towards their effective and unobtrusive monitoring.

The deliverable takes into account initial use case scenarios, as defined in the deliverable D2.1, which were based on the outcomes of conducted surveys and interviews with workers and stakeholders in the pilot working environments. It is important to mention that a further update of the use case scenarios will take place during the next months of the project, which will be based on survey outcomes from a significant number of representative participants, and will be reported in D2.6. As a result of the future update of the use case scenarios, the final outcomes of Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 will be reported in the deliverable D4.2. The presented extensible and modular framework facilitates the development of digital health and work ability tools, according to such evolving requirements. The outcomes of deliverable D3.1 which provided the insights on important human factors regarding employees' work ability, quality of life and job performance were also taken into account in the present deliverable. As a result, lifestyle, mental health and physical health indicators derived from the use of mobile devices were considered, and important interventions highlighted within interviews with workers in D3.1, such as short breaks at work, are presented as scenarios, thereby showing the applicability of the implemented framework.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows. Chapter 2 presents the rationale of the developed framework. Chapter 3 provides the design of the framework in terms of description of main architectural elements, and integration with other software components. Chapter 4 provides details on the activity and behavior

monitoring of individuals through the framework, describing the information flow in developed pipelines, and illustrating scenarios. Chapter 5 presents digital health tools and use case studies based on the developed framework, and Chapter 6 concludes the deliverable.

2. Framework Rationale

2.1 Importance of a Mobile-based Framework for Multimodal Data Collection

Over the past few years, mobile Internet-linked devices have increased in numbers and offered a plethora of possibilities for pervasive monitoring of health and well-being [1]. Smartphones, smartwatches and additional mobile devices for the monitoring of health parameters and the workplace environment, with constantly increasing networking and processing capabilities, have been introduced in our daily lives towards enabling better self-monitoring, promoting self-reflection, and improving health.

Traditionally, data for health monitoring of individuals are collected through self-reports and answers to given questions. This approach may often be limited due to memory constraints and recall bias [2]. Nowadays, smartphones emerge as the main means for health and well-being monitoring both at home and the workplace, because of their wide uptake even by older populations [3], as well as their capabilities for sensing, which allow the unobtrusive gathering of rich personalized information in naturalistic contexts. In this light, mobile phones can be utilized for digital phenotyping [4], i.e., 'moment-by-moment quantification of the individual-level human phenotype in situ', facilitating to develop markers to diagnose and treat diseases.

2.2 Exemplary Research Efforts

There have been several research efforts for pervasive and unobtrusive monitoring of health and well-being utilizing diverse behavior parameters captured by mobile devices. Canzian et al. [5], through the usage of location-related data, have managed to find significant correlations between the smartphone-driven features and the disease state of patients with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD). Wang et al. [6], reported significant predictors for personality traits, with data derived from mobile application which recorded activity data, conversations (number and duration), smartphone usage and location. A different source of data, derived from smart-screen keyboard typing dynamics seems to be able to correlate mental disorder scores for MDD [7], Bipolar Disorder [8] and Parkinson's disease [9], associating psychomotor retardation with keyboard typing. Additionally, the employment of multimodal sensing capabilities, often can increase the accuracy of diagnostic outcomes [10]. Chen et al. [11], combining different sources of information from location, activity, typing, surveys and phone usage features managed to accurately distinguish the patients with Mild Cognitive Impairment or Alzheimer's Disease from healthy controls. Therefore, behavioral parameters captured by mobile device such as location, physical activity and keyboard typing dynamics, can be important towards diagnosis of diseases.

Mobile devices can also be used in the context of building digital health interventions towards the primary or secondary prevention of diseases [12], [13]. In this direction, the regular monitoring of behavioral parameters such as physical activity, are indispensable towards personalized coaching, preventing sedentary behavior, and improving the well-being and work ability of ageing workers [14]. A significant

number of mobile-based physical activity interventions with underactive adults or seniors have been found to be effective [15]. Regular breaks at work and promotion of daily walking at workplaces have been recommended [16], [17].

2.3 Ageing@Work Framework Novelty

Despite the value of mobile devices in everyday health monitoring anywhere-anytime, mobile-based frameworks for multimodal data collection, which are first and foremost required for the development of digital health tools and interventions for better quality of life and work ability, have been remarkably limited. Dario et al. [18], presented an open mobile health platform for data collection based mainly on surveys and third-party apps such as Apple HealthKit. Torous et al. [19], developed a platform designed specifically for psychiatry, mainly through the collection of surveys, location and accelerometer data. Other mobile tools have merely relied on sampling subject experiences through self-reports and ecological momentary assessment methods [20], [21].

In this direction, our aim was to develop a mobile-based multimodal framework for pervasive health monitoring, aiming to contribute in the systematic design and development of digital health platforms requiring to collect data in the wild anywhere (home, workplace, on-the-move) and anytime. In contrast with previous research efforts, our framework supports capturing of a very rich set of data sources for the workers, including activity information from wearable devices, smartphones, and third-party apps (e.g., widely-used apps such as Google Fit and Samsung Health), keystroke typing data, location information, data from medical and environmental IoT devices, and self-reports. All these data sources can be utilized in the context of building a variety of digital health applications according to evolving needs and requirements. Our framework could also be particularly valuable in the development of mobile health systems during the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond, considering the increased use of digital tools on the one hand [22], and the requirement for close health monitoring of individuals living under lockdown measures on the other [23], [24].

3. Multimodal Framework Design and Development

This section is dedicated to the description of the abstraction middleware framework, the multimodal data collection component that enables communication and data management for distributed applications. In accordance with the project’s requirements, regarding the activity and behaviour monitoring, it is expected that the middleware framework will couple our system’s automated activity recognition module along with existing third-party applications, utilizing mainly their sensing modalities and data collection components, as they facilitate the activity and behavior recognition process, as well as the initial formulation and maintenance of workers’ data profile (Virtual Worker Model).

3.1 Middleware Objectives

In order to build a context-aware application, capable of rule-based decision-making, the proposed architecture has to be able to support multimodal data collection. Combining the information derived from many different modalities in an unobtrusive and meaningful way, such as activity recognition with location’s context, offers a plethora of possibilities for context-driven decision algorithms, the outcomes of which could be outputted towards the users through the Virtual Coach and improve the ageing worker’s self-management of healthy habits and goals. In that direction the proposed abstraction middleware framework architecture must encapsulate data derived from both existing third-party applications, which the users could possibly use prior to the development of this system, and new implemented modalities for the needs of Ageing@Work. Accessing the data should be possible not only from users’ personal phone but from anywhere they wish to. In that essence, as well as for research purposes, the data derived from using the mobile application should populate the worker’s Virtual User Model (wVUM), which can be considered to act in our context as the database where collected data is stored.

The following diagram depicts part of the Ageing at Work architecture that describes the flow between the layers that are associated with the data collection in the abstraction middleware framework.

Figure 1. Abstracted system flow

3.2 Middleware Architecture and Components

The middleware is the central component of the system, which is connected with all the different modalities and decides which of them will be enabled/disabled at any time. Data storing, information exchanges and context combination are regulated by the middleware. The diagram below depicts the Middleware architecture, all the different components connecting with it and the data flow between them.

Figure 2. System Architecture

In the above diagram, we can group all the components into two large categories, those that are included inside the Ageing@Work mobile application and those that are separated from the application and communicate over Rest-full logic. Components such as the VUM and the Healthcare Platform, require the authentication of each user in order to exchange data, through the authentication-token provided by login mechanism. In the following sections each of the built-in or external components will be described in detail.

3.2.1 Smartphone Component

The mobile application accommodates the middleware and all the modalities created specifically for the needs of this project. Hosting the middleware inside the mobile application offers low latency benefits, since all the data are stored locally and no constant communication with an external server is needed. Also, by deploying the middleware inside the phone, extra levels of data privacy are ensured since decision algorithms that would need sensitive data, such as exact location coordinates, won't need to share them with an external server.

3.2.1.1 Middleware

The components that are included inside the middleware are depicted in the figure below and will be explained below.

Figure 3. Middleware components.

1. Controller component

The controller is the brain of the system. This component is an all-time running foreground service, which decides which of the rest components will be enabled, exchanges data with them, stores the data inside a local database and decides which of the events should be outputted to the users. The controller receives raw data from the rest of the modalities through the *Low-Level Data Receiver*, which actually operates as a broadcast receiver.

2. Low Level Data Receiver component

All the individual modalities are set to broadcast messages upon new data and this component is registered to listen those events. When a new update arrives, this component transfers the data to the *Controller*.

3. Areas Database

Includes location sensitive data such as personal addresses and locations visited with their latitudes, longitudes. This table is not shared with the server but is needed locally to be able to keep track of places visited by the user. An example of the table is shown below:

Areas Database								
NAME (<i>unique</i>)	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE	DINSTANCE_BETWEEN_CENTER_AND_POI	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	ADDRESS	HASHED_ADDRESS	DATETIME
WORK	40.5650 264	22.9950 101	0	WORKPLACE	WORKPLACE	Thermi 570 01, Greece	4ac680576633e308cb6b1ecd961c29 deceadedb1345....	16006280 40706
newPoint10	40.6160 267	22.9603 4	6.922787319 840222	SOCIAL	BAR	Katsimi di 4, Thessaloniki 546 39, Greece	3094fe1293749f78041e195807d4bdc bf7c0c503b13d...	16015784 15938
activityPOI15	40.6165 987	22.9735 155	17.84015920 596095	TRANSPORT	BUSSTOP	Ipatias 22, Thessaloniki 543 51, Greece	cd6a8b721c4c34234c79514dde5b3d a....	16013059 01887

Table 2. Areas Database example

- NAME: A unique name provided by the application, WORK/HOME addresses provided by the user while newPoint(number) indicate locations saved when the user was for at least 10 minutes inside a radius of 100 meters from this location and finally activityPOI(number) a location that was saved during an activity path tracking.
- LATITUDE: The latitude of the location.
- LONGITUDE: The longitude of the location:
- DINSTANCE_BETWEEN_CENTER_AND_POI: The real-world distance in meters from the location the system assumed as a new point of interest and the nearest location entry from the Location Context API, which provided the category and subcategory.
- CATEGORY: The category of the closest in distance location provided by the Location Context API, stored in the current database. (SOCIAL/ EDUCATION/ HEALTH/ SHOP/ etc....)
- SUBCATEGORY: The subcategory of the closest in distance location provided by the Location Context API, stored in the current database. (BAR/ COLLEGE/ CLINIC/ BAKERY/etc....)
- ADDRESS: The real-world address as obtained for this latitude and longitude.
- HASHED_ADDRESS: A Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA)-256 encrypted string using the ADDRESS as input. This information can be used to correlate same location entries without knowing the actual address or latitude and longitude.
- DATETIME: The time in UNIX milliseconds when this entry was added to the table.

4. Events Database

This database stores all the events related with activities, locations, scenarios, path tracking, keyboard dynamics and mood self-reports. **Activity events** include information about when an activity started and when ended. **Locations events** consist of entrance/exit events from known locations. **Scenario**

events describe when the user was notified for a specific scenario and if he succeeded or failed to follow the advice. **Path tracking** events store location information combining activities (e.g., Activity “Running” at category “Leisure” with subcategory “Park”). **Keyboard events** are referring to keyboard dynamics related data for each keyboard session. Finally, **Questionnaire events** store self-reports of the user’s mood and physical state.

Location Events Table								
ID (unique)	DATETIME	NAME	HASHED_ADDRESS	EVENT_TYPE	DISTANCE_BETWEEN_CENTER_AND_POI	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	SEND_TIME
1	1601305664039	HOME	d50e016aa58cb95d7...	ENTRANCE	0.0	HOME	HOME	1601305685962
2	1601356308226	HOME	d50e016aa58cb95d7363b0025...	EXIT	0.0	HOME	HOME	1601410352000
3	1601400332000	activityPOI15	cd6a8b721c4c34234c79514dd...	ENTRANCE	17.84015920596095	TRANSPORT	BUSSTOP	1601403131000

Table 3. Location Events table example

- ID: A unique id for each entry.
- DATETIME: The date time in UNIX milliseconds when the event occurred.
- NAME: Location name as stored inside the Areas Database.
- HASHED_ADDRESS: An SHA-256 encrypted string using the ADDRESS as input. This information can be used to correlate same location entries without knowing the actual address or latitude and longitude.
- EVENT_TYPE: Indicates the type of the event. For Location Events this can be INIT_APP (when the app restarts), ENTRANCE and EXIT.
- DISTANCE_BETWEEN_CENTER_AND_POI: The real-world distance in meters from the location the system assumed as a new point of interest and the nearest location entry from the Location Context API which provided the category and subcategory.
- CATEGORY: The category of the closest in distance location provided by the Location Context API, stored in the current database. (SOCIAL/ EDUCATION/ HEALTH/ SHOP/ etc....)
- SUBCATEGORY: The subcategory of the closest in distance location provided by the Location Context API, stored in the current database. (BAR/ COLLEGE/ CLINIC/ BAKERY/etc....)
- SEND_TIME: A date time in UNIX milliseconds indicating the send of this entry to the server, as to not resend it.

Activity Events Table				
ID (unique)	DATETIME	NAME	EVENT_TYPE	SEND_TIME
19	1601272735926	WALKING	START	1601273876109
20	1601272766668	WALKING	STOP	1601273876324
21	1601272766677	STILL	START	1601273877996
22	1601273203453	STILL	STOP	1601273881821
23	1601273203483	IN_VEHICLE	START	1601273884923
24	1601273601107	IN_VEHICLE	STOP	1601273886321
25	1601273601119	STILL	START	1601273886520
26	1601273632938	STILL	STOP	1601273886736
27	1601273632988	IN_VEHICLE	START	1601273887108
28	1601273696093	IN_VEHICLE	STOP	1601273887526

Table 4. Activity Events table example

- NAME: Activity name as provided by the Google Activity Recognition API.
- EVENT_TYPE: Indicates the type of the event. For Activity Events this can be INIT_APP (when the app restarts), START and STOP.

Path Tracking Events Table									
ID (unique)	NAME	DATETIME	HASHED_ADDRESS	ACTIVITY_NAME	ACTIVITY_DURATION	LAT_LONG_LIST (NOT SHARED WITH SERVER)	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	SEND_TIME
14	WORK	1601303327360	4ac680576633e308cb6b...	WALKING	463837	[[40.5654681,22.9952031],[40.5679396,22.9966625],[40.5663942,22.9958525],[40.5678515,22.9967082]]	WORKPLACE	WORKPLACE	1601303327360
15	activityPOI14	1601305362585	2cd02acbafeb01c76fed5a4e...	WALKING	1584088	[[40.5993655,22.9707874],[40.6001016,22.9703141], ...]	UNKNOWN	UNKNOWN	1601303328132

16	activityPOI15	1601305901863	cd6a8b721c4c34234c79514...	WALKING	478794	[[40.6165987,22.9735155],[40.6185125,22.9747358],[40.6191203,22.9751136], ...]	TRANSPORT	BUSSTOP	1601303329072
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Table 5. Path Tracking Events table example

- **NAME:** Name according to the location stored in the Areas Database. The center for each path tracking was calculated as the single location, from the list of locations recorder while path tracking, which within a radius (ex 100 meters) included the maximum number of other locations from the same path.
- **HASHED_ADDRESS:** Hashed address as stored in the Areas Database.
- **ACTIVITY_NAME:** Most common activity among the activities during the path tracking.
- **ACTIVITY_DURATION:** Duration of the path tracking in milliseconds.
- **LAT_LONG_LIST:** A list of all the locations recorded during the activity. This information is never sent to the server but only used locally to compute the center and characterize the location accordingly.
- **CATEGORY:** Most common category from all the locations recording during the path tracking, as derived from the Location Context API.
- **SUBCATEGORY:** Most common subcategory from all the locations recording during the path tracking, from the Location Context API.

Scenario Events Table				
ID (unique)	DATETIME	NAME	EVENT_TYPE	SEND_TIME
19	1601299921498	BREAK_AT_WORK	NOTIFIED	1601299921498
20	1601302981381	BREAK_AT_WORK	SUCCESS	1601299922551
21	1601303152832	LEISURE_WALK	NOTIFIED	1601299921633
22	1601305663957	STAIRS	NOTIFIED	1601299921712
24	1601305994439	STAIRS	FAILED	1601299921853
25	1601308969534	BREAK_AT_WORK	NOTIFIED	1601299921945
26	1601312856996	BREAK_AT_WORK	FAILED	1601299922049

Table 6. Scenario Events table example

- **NAME:** Name of the event. Possible names for the Scenarios Events are BREAK_AT_WORK, LEISURE_WALK, STAIRS and INIT_APP (when the application restarts).
- **EVENT_TYPE:** The type of the event. Possible event types are NOTIFIED, SUCCESS, FAILED and INIT_APP (when the application restarts).

Keyboard Events Table			
ID (unique)	DATETIME	SESSION_DATA	SEND_TIME
1	1607954726915	{ "CurrentAppName": "Messenger", "CurrentCountry": "GR", "CurrentIMEI": "dc8dc24c0ccf6b30", "CurrentLanguage": "el", "Distance": [53.55022923402888, 2.4112107425256566, 45.80250806793966, ...], "DownTime": [137990256, 137990968, 137991114, ...], "DownTimeDelete": [137990977, 137991119, ...], "IsLongPress": [0, 0, 0, ...], "IsShowPopupOn": false, "IsSoundOn": false, "IsVibrationOn": true, "KeyboardScale": 0.9, "NumDels": 5, "PressureValue": [1.0, 1.0, 1.0, ...], "StartDateTime": 1607954708012, "StopDateTime": 1607954726849, "UpTime": [137990423, 137991019, 137991198, 137991571, ...], "UpTimeDelete": [137991023, 137991201, ...], "VibrationDuration": 10 }	null

Table 7. Keyboard Events table example

- SESSION_DATA: Contains information about keystroke timing series data along with current settings and information in JSON format.

Questionnaire Events Table				
ID (unique)	DATETIME	NAME	QUESTIONNAIRE_ANSWERS	SEND_TIME
1	1607954738321	MOOD_ZOOM	{ "Data": { "Description": "Please rate to what extend the following words describe your mood through the day:", "Name": "Mood Zoom", "Questions": [{"QuestionText": "Anxious", "QuestionDescription": "(worried; nervous)", "QuestionOrder": 0, "QuestionOptions": [{"Description": "Not at all", "Points": 0, "OptionOrder": 0, "selected": false}, ...] }, ...] }	null

Table 8. Questionnaire Events table example

- NAME: The name of the questionnaire.
- QUESTIONNAIRE_ANSWERS: Contains the answers of the questionnaire in JSON format.

5. Third-party Database

This database stores all the data collected through 3rd party applications and the Smartwatch measurements. Such data might be heart-rate measurements, sleep related info, total steps per day and others. These data are saved into a MongoDB within blob files.

6. Http Requests component

This component includes various methods for regulating the data transfer between the middleware and the Rest-full APIs. Http calls have to be made in specific turn sometimes, for example when sending data to the VUM, the location data must be categorized first through calling an external Rest-API, essentially giving a latitude-longitude pair and receiving Category, Subcategory and distance from the

given point to the nearest location stored to the database. Then the middleware can send the data categorized to VUM.

7. Self-Reporting Component

During the initial setup of the application, the participants are enabled to provide demographic information, as well as answers to selected questionnaires, which can be used to collect baseline information. In addition, periodic self-reports at provided intervals (e.g., daily) are supported. For example, the Mood Zoom Questionnaire [25] can be used for self-reporting mood, which has demonstrated promising adherence results and strong correlation with established clinical questionnaires.

8. Event-Detection Component

According to the information provided, rule-based decision algorithms are employed, the result of which is being passed back to the middleware. Then the middleware might decide to inform the user through the Virtual Coach, store the information into the database or ignore it. Having the detection of high-level events in a different component than the *Controller*, offers flexibility in the code and makes the system more resilient to changes. In addition, if the same system would be used for different scenarios tracking according to the contextual information, the only change would be to implement a different Event Detection component or add new rule-based decision algorithms to the existing ones. More information about the rule-based algorithms and the scenarios implemented inside the Event Detection component will be discussed in Chapter 5.

3.2.1.2 Built-in Modalities

For the needs of Ageing@Work, many different libraries and modules were implemented. All the different modules which are built inside the Ageing@Work application are shown in the figure below.

Figure 4. Built-in Modalities

1. Location Tracking Library:

Implements a service, which tracks the user’s location (latitude, longitude) every N second, using cellular network or GPS if it is available. Also provides methods for geocoding, such as to find addresses from coordinates and the opposite. Furthermore, if the middleware decides to, it can increase the interval of location requests for battery saving.

2. Activity Tracking Library:

Contains two different services, one for generic and one for scenario specific activity tracking. More details about activity tracking will be presented in Chapter 5.

a. Google Activity Recognition component:

This service handles methods provided by Google for tracking user’s activity. The API recognizes seven classes of activities: “in vehicle”, “on bicycle”, “still”, “tilting”, “on foot”, “walking” and

“running”. The activity recognition works for any phone position-orientation and has battery optimizations implemented already by Google.

b. CNN model component:

Using the UCI Human Activity Recognition (HAR) dataset [26], a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) model was built, which is able to detect four classes: “walking”, “upstairs”, “downstairs” and “still”. This additional service offers the chance to track specific scenarios such as stair climbing. While the service is running, the phone asks for accelerometer and gyroscope raw data every 50ms, which results into battery drain. For that reason, this service is only enabled for short periods of time when a specific scenario needs stair climbing information.

3. Keyboard:

The implemented keyboard is built using the Android Open-Source Project (AOSP) files and it is identical with the keyboard that was prebuilt on android phones before GBoard’s existence. Currently google has stopped working on this keyboard and renamed their keyboard as GBoard, which is no longer open source. Due to many years of development, AOSP keyboard is a well-built option, which includes many of the modern keyboard features like word prediction and auto correct. For the project needs, this keyboard was customized to log keystroke timing related data, such as the time a key was pressed and the time of its release. Additional features, like keyboard resizing and custom dictionaries were added.

3.2.2 External Components

3.2.2.1 Third-party Applications

As a first step in the middleware design, we evaluated some of the health and life support applications that are available on the market focusing on ones that a) are able to successfully detect some of the activities we are interested in monitoring, b) provide an API that collects all information needed for our Virtual Worker Model component, c) optionally allow the transmission of raw data (accelerometer, gyroscope and other sensors’ information) to our system application, d) are paired with a corresponding smartwatch that provides the desired health metrics. Accommodating third-party applications in the proposed system can offer valuable information already captured from those apps.

Within this context, the conducted research resulted in the selection of Google Fit and Samsung Health app that comes with the Samsung’s Galaxy Watch, as possible options for data collection in the context of the A@W data collection framework. As such, the system currently takes advantage of Samsung Health and Google Fit. Both applications can provide data related to step counting, activity tracking, sleep monitoring and heart rate measurements, while Samsung Health can also provide information for water intake and floors climbed. The system receives data from the Samsung Health using the provided *Samsung Health SDK*, while communication with Samsung smartwatches is enabled via the *Samsung Accessory SDK*. Finally, the connection with Google fit is succeed via the *Google Fitness API*.

3.2.2.2 Location Context API

This API was created for the needs of Ageing@Work. By providing a location's latitude and longitude, contextual information about this location will be provided. This API was implemented using OpenStreetMap's open source [27] csv files, which later was transformed into a local database. Each location stored into the database has a Category and a Subcategory. The locations can be either individual points, declared by a single pair of latitude and longitude, or whole areas created by combinations of points. The API can receive requests which include at least a latitude-longitude pair and a limit which indicates the number of POIS to return. It is also possible to query for a specific category or subcategory and to provide the maximum distance for which the results will be included.

An HTTP call might include the following variables and a few examples are provided below:

- lat: Point of interest latitude. (mandatory)
- long: Point of interest longitude. (mandatory)
- limit: Number of results to return. (mandatory)
- category: Contextual categorization of the nearest location.
- subcategory: Contextual sub-categorization of the nearest location.
- Distance: Maximum real-world distance in meters, within which radius the search will be done. Default is 20 meters when no category or subcategory are provided, else it will be 2.5km.

a.	https://[hidden-ip]/greece/?lat=40.620407799&long=22.9754239&limit=2&category=SPORT&subcategory=STADIUM
1.	{ "NAME": "Achileas Triandrias", "CATEGORY": "SPORT", "SUBCATEGORY": "STADIUM", "LON": 22.974751, "LAT": 40.620883, "DISTANCE": 77.56915408352558},
2.	{ "NAME": "Εθνικό Καυτανζόγλειο Στάδιο", "CATEGORY": "SPORT", "SUBCATEGORY": "STADIUM", "LON": 22.9669483949153, "LAT": 40.62553013530415, "DISTANCE": 914.3392034139785}}
b.	https://[hidden-ip]/greece/?lat=40.61305&long=22.95096&distance=2500&limit=3
1.	{ "NAME": "Ο Κήπος του Οδυσσέα Φωκά", "CATEGORY": "LANDUSE", "SUBCATEGORY": "PARK", "LON": 22.95161112350707, "LAT": 40.612945389119375, "DISTANCE": 56.17653816285729},
2.	{ "NAME": "Παραλία Θεσσαλονίκης", "CATEGORY": "CULTURAL", "SUBCATEGORY": "PEDESTRIAN", "LON": 22.950602995155627, "LAT": 40.61389989759319, "DISTANCE": 99.18780493951913},
3.	{ "NAME": "Γενικό Προξενείο της Ομοσπονδιακής Δημοκρατίας της Γερμανίας", "CATEGORY": "PUBLICSERVICE", "SUBCATEGORY": "EMBASSY", "LON": 22.95260123407835, "LAT": 40.613369032144256, "DISTANCE": 143.00021922109073}}
c.	https://[hidden-ip]/greece/?lat=40.559143&long=23.035824&limit=1
1.	{ "NAME": "Φράγμα θέρμης", "CATEGORY": "LEISURE", "SUBCATEGORY": "PARK", "LON": 23.03565324069628, "LAT": 40.55714116911095, "DISTANCE": 223.04968570259402}}

Table 9. Location Context API example calls

Even though this API presents an open-source and cost-free solution for location categorization, one can argue that it doesn't have the robustness of market solutions such as the Google Maps API, since OpenStreetMap's database is smaller and less frequently updated. In order to scale up, steering towards other solutions could be considered, taking also into account the additional cost per location request.

3.2.2.3 Healthcare Platform API

The Healthcare platform API accommodates the functionality for the users to overview their collected data, aggregated over a selected period of time. All the different data sources, from third party or built-in data collection, can be overviewed per category with graphs. Also, within this API users can register their IoT devices, such as smart-scales or Blood Glucose and Pressure Monitoring Systems, and collect data derived from those through a connection with the Eliot Hub cloud service [28]. Additionally, there are tools for the managers to including new questionnaires and demographic questions for the application's enrollment procedure. Moreover, clinical data, such as those derived from the medical IOT devices are stored in a separate database, respecting data privacy under the Health Level Seven protocol (HL7) [29], whereas each authorized client requires users' consent to access their data. Finally, in the context of interoperability with Electronic Health Records, the system supports the HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard, as shown in Table 10, concerning data acquisition from a smart weight scale.

Healthcare Platform API		
Smart Scales	Temperature Sensors	Humidity Sensors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humidity • Weight • Temperature 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data overview • Questionnaires • Demographics

```
{...
  "component": [
    {
      "code": {
        "coding": [
          {
            "system": "http://loinc.org",
            "code": "3141-9",
            "display": "Weight Measured"
          }
        ],
        "text": "Weight Measured"
      },
      "valueQuantity": {
        "value": 101,
        "unit": "kg",
        "system": "http://unitsofmeasure.org",
        "code": "kg"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Table 10. Example of data derived from smart scale in HL7-FHIR format

3.2.2.4 Virtual User Model (VUM)

The VUM is the workers’ data space, which stores and, in an essence, models their behavioral identity. All the above data mentioned earlier collected either by the location, activity, scenarios, path tracking events, keyboard data or questionnaires are stored on SQLite database inside the phone. Whenever WIFI is available these data are sent to VUM. Raw/Sensitive data are stored only on the phones database (e.g., location addresses, latitude, longitude). The actual location is never sent to the server, instead only category/ subcategory and a SHA-256 hashed address is sent. This encoding allows us to track same addresses without knowing the actual address. For example, if user deletes the app and installs again, the locations “nicknames” sent to server might change but the hashed address will be the same, without ever knowing the actual address or the actual location name.

Moreover, since identical data are provided from multiple sources, such as the steps or activities from built-in modalities and multiple third-party apps, they are stored in VUM under a unified abstraction scheme. This allows data retrieval, according to available sources, using the same data representation design, defining only the feature to be retrieved and a period (start and end) in UNIX timestamps.

```

{"message": "still_data",
 "data": [
  {
    "id": 2039,
    "user_id": 4,
    "activity": "still",
    "raw_data": null,
    "unit": "activityType",
    "start_time": 1599812957,
    "end_time": 1599820950,
    "created_at": "2020-09-11 14:03:59",
    "updated_at": "2020-09-11 14:03:59",
    "steps": null,
    "heart_rate": null,
    "nutrition": null,
    "calories": 189.59812927246,
    "distance": 0
  }
], "status": 200}

```

Table 11. JSON form for activities as returned from server

Finally, the VUM API handles user authentication, as this is the main server of the application. Using their credentials, the users can login into the application and other APIs like the Healthcare Platform API (Dashboard) where they can see data aggregated in graphs. The data exchange requests are handled over HTTPs secure protocol with mandatory authentication of the user, using the time-limited token acquired from the login mechanism, while for research purposes the data are shared anonymized providing only an arbitrary incremental id (sequential according to registration order in the database). The server is currently located within the district of Center for Research and Technology Hellas.

In the following table the data collected from all the individual modules are presented. All these data, as already mentioned, are first stored in the personal mobile phone database and later send to the external databases (VUM or Healthcare Platform).

Name	Data	Information
Location Tracking Library	Latitude, Longitude, Address <i>(raw/sensitive, not shared)</i>	Uses cellular network or GPS. Utility methods for geocoding. Batter optimizations
Activity Tracking Library	Google Activity Recognition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walking, Still, Running, In Vehicle, On Bicycle, Tilting CNN model: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walking, Still, Upstairs, Downstairs 	Googles Activity Recognition API: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation/Position independent. • Battery optimization implemented. CNN model using UCI HAR dataset: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation/Position specific implementation. • Battery restricted.
Location Context API	Locations Category and Subcategory	Custom API that uses OpenStreetMap's Open-Source csv files, combined in a database table per country.
Keyboard	Press Time, Release Time, Distance, Deletion	Uses customized Android Open-Source Project files offering many modern features, while also records key stroke Time Sequences.
Self-Reports	Users are prompted to answer demographic related questions. Additionally, questionnaires for personality traits, depression and daily mood reports are included.	Users are prompted to answer demographic related questions. Additionally, questionnaires for personality traits, depression and daily mood reports are included.
Healthcare Platform API	Weight, Humidity, Luminescence, Temperature, Questionnaires creation tools, Medical Devices <i>(medical devices' data stored under HL7 protocol)</i>	Receives IoT derived data and store them under strict protocols. Furthermore, offers data visualization over aggregated periods for the users and management tools for the administration.
Samsung Accessory SDK	Accelerometer, Gyroscope, Heart rate	Provides Service for raw data retrieval from Samsung Smartwatches
Samsung Health SDK	Steps, Water intake, Activities, Floors Climbed, Heart rate, Sleep stages	Provides various health / activity related data while using Samsung phone or smartwatch.
Google Fit	Steps, Sleep Metrics, Activities, Heart rate	Provides various health / activity related data while using an Android phone.
VUM	Provides: Login credentials Stores: All the data except raw locations (latitude, longitude, addresses) and IOT/medical which are stored in Healthcare Platform.	All the above data collected by the middleware are stored on SQLite database inside the phone. Periodically, if Wi-Fi is available, these data are sent to VUM. Additionally, methods for a notification broadcast system are provided.

Table 12. Modalities Overview

4. Worker Activity and Behavior Tracking

4.1 Behavior Monitoring

The multimodal framework has been designed to record multimodal data unobtrusively in the wild, while it also provides contextual information about the user's behavior, so as to offer a personalized user experience. The presented system attempts to capture several mobile data sources which have been deemed to be important for health and well-being in the scientific literature, such as location, human activity, and interaction with mobile phones. In this context, we have combined custom pipelines for activity and behavior tracking, which provide opportunities for the development of different real-time monitoring tools and interventions. The collection of passively generated data from third-party applications further reinforces the multimodal monitoring of the workers.

In the next sub-sections, the initial implemented activity tracking solution will be presented along with the pipeline for location and activity data collection. Moreover, three specific scenarios will be presented, combining many different components of the architecture, aiming to show different interventions towards better health and work ability which can be utilized. The final version of the worker activity and behavior monitoring framework will be presented in the subsequent project deliverable, D4.2.

4.2 Human Activity Recognition

In the effort of building our own intelligent system, that will be able to efficiently detect low level activities as well as capture some behavioral context, we started by examining the state-of-the-art (Chapter 8.1, Appendix) approaches on simple activities such as walking, walking upstairs, sitting etc., with the purpose of firstly, reproduce those high accuracy results found in literature, and secondly, investigate the most appropriate method and corresponding parameters selection for our solution, considering that this activity recognition module will run constantly in our application.

According to the literature, one of the most promising methods for Human Activity Recognition (HAR) is the exploitation of Convolution Neural Networks (CNN). Towards this direction our attempts focused on recognizing additional classes of activities such as walking upstairs and downstairs, which were not provided by common APIs like Google's Activity Recognition API.

For our initial approach UCI HAR public dataset was used for training and testing, which contains data from six basic activities: Walking, walking upstairs, walking downstairs, standing, laying and sitting. Since the usage of the CNN model were focusing mostly two specific scenario tracking, like Stair Climbing detection, it was decided to exclude standing and laying classes, since they are identical with sitting in terms of immobility, ending up with four activities for the training. The dataset provides accelerometer and gyroscope data, sampled at 50 Hz. As a preprocessing step, we applied a median filter and then a three-order low pass Butterworth with 20Hz cut-off frequency, for noise reduction. Then, in order to derive the

gravity component from the accelerometer data, we applied a low pass Butterworth filter with 0.3Hz cut off frequency. Next, we segmented the 3-axis body-accelerometer and gyroscope into 128-valued window length with 50% overlap, resulting to six features. Other than those signals, we also used the magnitude for both accelerometer and gyroscope resulting in eight features in total. All the features were normalized subtracting the mean and dividing the standard deviation of each feature.

The UCI HAR data set's size is 4571 examples for training, obtained from 21 subjects, and 1878 examples for testing, obtained from 9 others, with split provided by the initial dataset. We tested various configurations for the CNN architecture. At first, we varied the layers from 1 to 4, keeping the kernel size fixed and equal to 2. We also trained with 3 layers and used 8, 16, 32 and 64 kernel sizes. Lastly, we tried training with 4 layers and kernel sizes 16, 32 and 64. The number of filters were set to 12*(Number of Layer), where Number of Layer refers to the index of the current layer. The last layer is a fully connected layer with 64 nodes. For all layers, we used ReLu as the activation function and SoftMax for the output layer. The best performance was obtained with 3 layers and 64 kernel size with accuracy reaching 0.97%. Table 13 shows the metrics for each activity along with the normalized confusion matrix:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
WALKING	0.9978	0.9153	0.9548	496
UPSTAIRS	0.9601	0.9703	0.9652	471
DOWNSTAIRS	0.9147	0.9952	0.9532	420
SITTING	1	0.998	0.999	491
accuracy			0.9686	1878
macro avg	0.9681	0.9697	0.968	1878
weighted avg	0.9703	0.9686	0.9686	1878

Table 13. CNN model raw signal results

Our first approach used raw accelerometer and gyroscope signals, which are orientation specific. Trying to minimize this problem, since the dataset consists from data recorded in waist-mounted positions and already poses a position-depended dataset, we tested the performance of the model when using only magnitude signals as features, which are orientation independent. With the same setup but with only two features now the model reached an accuracy of 95%, as shown in Table 14, with recall above 90%, for both Upstairs and Downstairs classes.

Although the results of both models are very high on metrics, the dataset that was modeled consisted of position-depended data. In real-world test where the users of the app would probably have the phone anywhere but on a waist-mounted phone clipper the actual accuracy is expected to degrade. For this reason, we must continue the research on the topic and examine other datasets, recorded from different phone positions or datasets for wearable ones.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
WALKING	0.9427	0.9617	0.9521	496
UPSTAIRS	0.8985	0.9023	0.9004	471
DOWNSTAIRS	0.9389	0.9143	0.9264	420
SITTING	1	0.998	0.999	491
accuracy			0.9457	1878
macro avg	0.945	0.9441	0.9445	1878
weighted avg	0.9457	0.9457	0.9457	1878

Table 14. CNN model results using magnitude

4.2.1 Google Activity Recognition API for HAR

The deep learning approach, which was described previously, is essential when tracking of additional activities, such as stair climbing, is needed, since other readily available solutions do not facilitate. In the other hand, the usage of Google’s Activity Recognition API constitutes a robust, widely used and well-optimized for battery savings activity tracking option. Unlike the custom deep learning approach, this API minimizes the battery drains as it does use only “short bursts” of sensory data in order to predict an activity. The activities the API can recognize are “In vehicle”, “On bicycle”, “Still”, “Tilting”, “On Foot”, “Walking” and “Running”, with overall accuracy reaching 0.83% when using a prediction threshold of 0.6 or more, according to Zhong Et al.[30]. Also, in their experiment they mention that “Tilting” and “Unknown” classes are the cause of misclassifications when cycling (32%) or stationary (32%) and when walking (15%) or running (10%).

One application can register for the usage of the API through native SDK library and activity prediction will be broadcasted to the application periodically. For example, the application can request updates every 15 seconds and according to the outputted probabilities of the aforementioned classes then can decide to choose the one with the highest prediction score or ignore some of them (ex. Unknown or Tilting classes). The fact that every application registered on this API will receive information for the same pool of data offers extended battery life since applications don’t need to read raw data from sensors which costs a lot of battery drain.

Since this API is accurate and offers well-handled battery optimizations, Google Activity Recognition API was chosen to be used for the Ageing@Work system as the main AR component. The interval of requesting updates was set to a minimum of 15 seconds but since battery optimizations apply, when the phone doesn’t move the API won’t provide any updates. The re-enable of the activity recognition begins by sudden movement of the phone. A choice was made also to not take notice of “Tilting” and “Unknown” classes, since they do not offer valuable information, while also as mentioned above are the cause of many misclassifications. Instead, we use these classes only for enabling the location tracking if it was disabled due to immobility, since “Tilting” is meant to warn for big changes in the phone orientation and thus informs for events where the phone is lifted from the desk.

Using this modality as the main AR component, the middleware, when informed for a new activity checks if another activity was started before. If consecutive activities are different then the first of the two has its event type marked as “STOP” and the last one as “START”. In this way in the database are stored sequential “START” and “STOP” for each activity, with timestamps to later count their duration.

4.3 Location Tracking

4.3.1 Location Updates Pipeline

In the next figure, the pipeline used for location information is depicted. After the initialization of the Middleware Service, its Controller component starts the Location Service, which provides location data (latitude and longitude) to the Controller through the Low Event Data Receiver. Then the data are passed to the Event Detection class where algorithms detect Entrance/Exit events within/from points of interest (POIs) and can save new locations as POIs if the user stays within an area long enough.

Figure 5. Location updates pipeline

4.3.2 Location Categorization Pipeline

Before sending any location data to VUM, the system checks if the locations have been categorized using the Location Context API. Any entry in the database, which has empty Category or Subcategory, is updated with context using the API. In detail, its latitude and longitude are being send in the API, which searches for POIs nearby these coordinates. If no specific category or subcategory is provided to the API it will return the closest POI regardless of category, else it will return only entries within this context. Also, the API offers the option to set radius which from the coordinates constructs the area 1of interest, within which the API will search for POIs.

In the case of categorization for locations, recorded during Path tracking, since many different locations are being recorded, each of these are sent to the API and the most common category and subcategory is selected. After receiving the location context, the Controller updates the location entries both in Areas and Events Database.

Figure 6. Location categorization pipeline

4.4 Activity Tracking

4.4.1 Activity Updates Pipeline

As previously described the current system implements an Activity Recognition Service which mainly uses the Google’s Activity Recognition API. After subscribing for activity updates to this API, the service receives updates within a predefined interval. Through the usage of the Low Event Data Receiver the Controller is being informed for updates in activities and pass the information to the Event Detection Class. Within this class it is checked if the new activity is different than the previously stored one and in the same time if its confidence surpasses a threshold. In that case the current activity is updated and through the Controller the activity information is stored in the Events Database. Whenever a new activity is stored in the Database, the previous ones’ status is tagged as STOP and the new ones as START with the current time-stamps.

Figure 7. Activity updates pipeline

4.4.2 Specific scenarios tracking

In the previous sections, the basic pipelines for location and activity tracking were described. Based on these updates the system is capable of tracking specific scenarios, through rule-based decision algorithms. The goal is to enrich users prospective of habits they have and are harmful in the long-term, as well as reinforce their beneficial ones.

4.4.2.1 Breaks at Work

It is important to take regular breaks at work to avoid prolonged immobility and prevent sedentary behavior. The importance of short breaks at work has been identified within interviews with workers in D3.1, and has been highlighted in the scientific literature [17]. Within this scope, the Ageing@Work system detects when the user is sitting for longer than one hour without any break for walk. In such case, the application prompts the user to take a break and to walk for five minutes. If succeed, the system will congratulate the user with a notification or will remind her again to take a break. Additionally, when the user presses the notification the main activity of the application will launch, and the Avatar will read the message.

Figure 8. Break at Work scenario pipeline

4.4.2.2 Stair climbing

As mentioned in the previous chapter, in addition to the Google Activity Recognition API the Ageing@Work application is using a CNN model to estimate user's current activity when needed. This provides the capability to develop custom activity recognition model, e.g., stair climbing, according to ongoing requirements in Ageing@Work. In contrast with the API, the CNN model can predict when the user is climbing (UPSTAIRS) or coming down from stairs (DOWNSTAIRS). The scenario starts with the user entering a known area with stairs (home or workplace). The system checks if he has climbed stairs over the last hours and if not the HAR service with CNN starts. The predicted activities are transferred to the Controller through the Low-Level Event Data Receiver and through methods implemented in the Event Detection class the system decides if the user has taken the stairs. In case the user took the stairs, the Controller will save a successful event for stair scenario. If ten minutes passed without a successful report of staircase, the event is saved as failed. In both cases, after 10 minutes, the HAR service with CNN is disabled since it is heavily draining the battery.

Figure 9. Stair climbing scenario pipeline

4.4.2.3 Path tracking

The system that was already described only saved a new POI if the user stays inside an area with predefined radius for a prolong period of time. What about the case where the user goes for a walk or exercise in a park and never in a specific area for enough time? In order to detect new Points of Interest (POIs) in such cases, the system is recording the user's location every few meters when he is walking or running. The recording stops if the user stops moving for a period of Y minutes (5 minutes). The center for

each path is calculated as the single location, from the list of locations recorded while path tracking, which within a radius (ex 100 meters) included the maximum number of other locations from the same path. Then the system checks if this location is already inside another saved known location, and saves it accordingly, else creates a new entry with empty category and subcategory which later, when Wi-Fi is available, will be characterized by the Location Context API. In the case of path tracking, as mentioned earlier the context for the center of the location is the outcome of the most common categories as resulted from categorizing all the locations included in the path.

The path tracking pipeline is combined with the leisure walk scenario, whereas the system checks if the user has walked N minutes today and prompts him/her to go for a leisure walk accordingly. Also congratulates the user if she reaches the goal for minutes walked. Later this scenario could be extended to congratulate the user when she visits a park or a new point of interest for exercise or suggest nearby places found in the Location Context API.

Figure 10. Path tracking scenario pipeline

5. Results

The proposed architecture was implemented for Android, since this is the most popular operating system for mobile devices and there are plenty of code resources enabling the creation of robust applications. For the backend, a Laravel server was deployed as it is a well-established and robust option, which offers extensibility and tools for documentation and testing. The Restful API for location categorization was chosen to be hosted inside a Docker environment, separated from the rest of the server, ensuring the exact location information is anonymized (no login required) and cannot be associated with specific users. The backend of the Healthcare Platform API was built using NodeJs/ Express because it offers great scalability and fast preprocessing with event-based modeling. The Healthcare Platform has direct access to the main server, but additionally encapsulates a different database based on HL7 protocol for medical data, with additional authorization scheme that requires user’s consent to share their medical data. A scenario of setting up a digital health application utilizing the developed framework is presented below.

At the initial setup of the application, after the users have logged in with their accounts, the enrolment procedure starts. The users are asked to review the Terms and Agreements within the app, whereas upon refusal of the terms, their data won’t be shared with the server. Also, they are prompt to fill-in demographic questions and baseline questionnaires. After the enrolment procedure is finished, the users are redirected to the main page (Fig. 1a). Within this page they can configure (Fig. 1c) the tracking options and enable the service. Inside this configuration, the users can save their home and work address, in order for the system to recognize these places. Additionally, they can navigate through the menu and overview their activity information from different sources (Fig. 1d). Finally, they are prompted to enable the provided keyboard, with a setup guide to do so.

Figure 11. a) Main Page, b) Leisure Walk, c) Tracking configuration, d) Google fit daily overview

To further demonstrate the proof-of-concept operation, feasibility and applicability of the developed framework, three case studies in the well-being domain have been currently integrated. The first being the **Break@Work scenario**, aiming to remind the importance of small breaks between immobility sessions. Secondly, the **Leisure walk scenario**, which according to users' specified goals of daily activity minutes, prompts them for an evening walk, in case they have not reached them. And finally, the **Stair climbing scenario**, during which, if an individual enters a known area with stairs (home or workplace), and has not taken the stairs during this day, the system suggests going by foot instead of using an elevator.

All these scenarios are combining multiple components of the system architecture, with the bases being the activity and location tracking components. The activity and location updates are transferred through the *Low-Level Data Receiver* to the *Controller* and then to the *Event Detection Class*. After, the results of rule-based decision algorithms are returned to the *Controller*, where it is decided to intervene or not. Upon scenario success or failure, the scenario states ("Notified", "Success" and "Failed") are stored into the database and the users are informed through text-to-speech via the *Virtual Coach* (Fig. 11b). Those scenarios, along with the option to overview their data within the Healthcare Platform API (Fig. 12), are aiming to enrich users perspective of habits they have and are harmful in the long-term, as well as reinforce their beneficial ones. Demonstrations of our implemented scenarios are shown in a series of YouTube videos¹.

Figure 12. Healthcare Platform API (Dashboard)

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJsxLGgNFnLi0e6B-FsK8bQ/videos>

6. Conclusions

The present deliverable describes the design and development of a mobile-based multimodal framework for pervasive health monitoring and behavior tracking, which will be used in the context of the AgeingAtWork project. The proposed architecture manages to capture information which can be associated with the behavioral patterns of workers, from a rich data space including multiple sources. The data collection is performed unobtrusively in the wild, while respecting data privacy, and promoting interoperability with external applications and services through a REST-based architecture. Further, our modular framework provides tools for easy adaptation to tailored monitoring applications, since it accommodates all the different modalities as add-on libraries. This facilitates to correspond to changing needs and requirements in the duration of the project, and after its completion. Our framework brings useful insights towards the design of similar frameworks for building pervasive health applications. Finally, the described case studies highlight useful digital health applications and worker interventions which can be developed based on the proposed framework.

7. References

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8. Appendix

In the present chapter, the state-of-art methods that fall in the context of human activity recognition, are described. The selected approaches that are reviewed here, focus on two research topics that are essential in the Ageing at Work project, with the first being, human daily activities and behaviors recognition, and the second being, the use of smart, wearable devices that can be used for this purpose.

8.1 Human Activity Recognition Literature

Understanding the state, behavior and surrounding context of humans has become important in recent years due to its contribution to various fields such as, security, surveillance, intelligent environments, health and elderly care, with the latter being our primal domain of interest. A significant amount of work has been done on human activity recognition with researchers focusing on many different approaches each time. These approaches can be broadly classified into vision-based and sensor-based, as shown below.

During the past years, sensor-based approaches received the most interest due to their unobtrusive and discrete manner for measuring data, as opposed to vision-based techniques which would require users' acceptance. Moreover, many practical limitations related to carry-on sensors like accelerometers and GPS-receivers have been resolved, mainly with the broad and systematic usage of smartphones. Nowadays almost none ever leaves house without carrying a smart-phone, while the fact that each phone is equipped with several sensors make them an adequate tool for activity recognition. In the sensor-based approach, different sensors are used to capture the behavior of human while they perform daily life activities, with the accelerometer gaining the most attention in the activity recognition research. However, in recent years, other sensors, like the gyroscope magnetometer, state of phone, GPS location information are combined in fusion-based methods, with the aim of improving activity recognition performance. Classifying activities from accelerometer and other sensors' data is essentially a data mining task that uses

machine-learning algorithms called as classifiers for training the data. This section presents a literature review on activity recognition studies involving smartphones' sensors and the areas of application.

An accelerometer is a sensor that returns a real value of acceleration along the x, y, or z-axis. The type of accelerometer (uniaxial, biaxial, or triaxial) is determined by the number of measurement axes. The generic concept of measurement of body movements with an accelerometer is discussed by Godfrey et al. [31] with reference to past studies and modern techniques. In one such study, Bouten et al. [32] recommended the position of waist or back as the appropriate place for attaching the sensor to minimize the influence of gravitational force on the accelerometer output. As an outcome of the study, accelerometers were deemed reliable for assessing physical activity levels because the signal magnitude area of the acceleration signal gave a good correlation ($r = 0.89$) with metabolic energy expenditure. An important application of this relationship was explored—the use of accelerometers to assign less physically demanding tasks for rehabilitating an injured worker by [33].

Extending activity recognition to real-world situations was carried out by Bao and Intille [34]. Classification accuracies with various machine learning algorithms were compared for classifying 20 everyday activities like working on a computer, climbing stairs, vacuuming, brushing teeth, and folding laundry by using data collected from five biaxial accelerometers set on various body positions. The decision tree classifier showed the best performance recognizing everyday activities with an overall accuracy of 84%. In another related work, Ravi et al. [35] found that combining multiple classifiers gave better performance than a single classifier for recognizing a set of eight activities with a single tri-axial accelerometer set near the pelvic zone. The activities studied included standing, walking, running, climbing upstairs, climbing down stairs, sit-ups, vacuuming and brushing teeth.

Recognition accuracy naturally increases with the number of sensors, but more sensors may be uncomfortable for the subject and could interfere with normal or spontaneous physical activity. So, another area of work has been to recognize activity with a minimum number of sensors. In general, it is difficult to recognize activities by using a single sensor, but Yang et al. [36] obtained an accuracy of 95% in classifying eight domestic activities by using neural classifiers and keeping the sensor module on the dominant wrist.

Activity recognition by accelerometers has also promising applications in health care and sports. Parkka et al. [37] studied different sensors suitable for developing an activity diary that included activities like lying, rowing, walking, sitting or standing, cycling, running, and Nordic walking. Accelerometers proved to be the most information-rich and accurate sensors for activity recognition. In another work, Ermes et al. [38] compared performances in instructed and uninstructed settings for recognizing sport activities like playing football, cycling and running from accelerometers on hip and wrist and GPS information.

Joshua and Varghese [39] were among the first researchers who explored the application of accelerometer in construction for work sampling. However, the scope of their work was limited to only a single bricklayer in a controlled environment. Moreover, their proposed framework used accelerometer as the sole source of motion data. Also, the necessity of installing wired sensors on the worker's body may introduce a constraint on the worker's freedom of movement.

Akhavian et al. [40] on the other hand, investigated the suitability of accelerometers in activity classification to automate the work-sampling process for evaluating labor productivity. In their

experimental scenario, the construction worker performs different activities, while in work, like walking, kneeling, fetching, lifting, pushing, placing, aligning and holding. Accelerometer and gyroscope data are retrieved through a smartphone placed in the upper right arm, that are further processed into hand-crafted features excessively used in literature such as, mean measure, standard deviation, entropy, spectral energy and correlation. Those features are later fed into multiple classifiers (Neural network, regression tree, K-nearest neighbors, logistic regression, SVMs) in order to compare classification methods. In the best-case scenario, they achieved over 90% accuracy in both user-dependent and independent cases.

There are also several sensor-based HAR systems for housekeeping tasks. In [41], Pham et al. proposed a framework to analyze low level food preparation task by Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), where the mechanism of template adaptation and threshold optimization are also proposed to deal with the issues in individual variability. Karaman S. et al. [42] developed a hierarchical two level Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) to detect and segment activities of interest. In [43] and [44], authors present a single accelerometer-based approach based on autoregressive (AR) modeling of the acceleration component signals, combining the AR-coefficients along with the signal-magnitude and tilt angle. Although the results of their method reach an average accuracy of 0.97 for fifteen type of activities, the method is position specific and there is no validation on mobile. In [45] authors address the specific position limitation, but the approach is still constrained by offline computing that excludes in-wild application of the method.

As noted, the accelerometer and gyroscope signal values vary highly when placed in different part of the body, even if the same activity is performed. In [46] authors, attempt to address this problem by designing a position independent activity recognition system, which uses only a smartphones' triaxial accelerometer. Its implementation differs due to the architecture used for the training part of the system, which uses statistical features for the first Level, L1, while in the lower layers, L3 to L4, using Principal Component Analysis the number of features is augmented and these layers increase in complexity.

Over the past years Deep Learning techniques for HAR have seen increase in research efforts, with Plotz et al. [47], being the first to use Restricted Boltzmann Machines, and others following [48]–[50] implementing models using slightly different methods. Duffner et al. [51], used combined accelerometer and gyroscope data to train Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for gesture recognition work and outperformed DTW and HMMs. Finally, Yang et al. [52] using several benchmarks, stated the higher performance of CNNs with hierarchical models for HAR .

In [53], the authors investigated if data specific normalization techniques and fusion of multimodal sensor data can help to create more robust Deep Learning HAR models. Their reporting suggests normalization techniques are increasing CNNs model performance and moreover, late and hybrid fusion techniques proved to be superior compared to early fusion techniques.

In [54] an unsupervised hybrid system for activity recognition is used with results similar to supervised implementations . One of the main concerns regarding human behavior modeling is data labelling, where raw data should be annotated with the corresponding label produced after monitoring a person's activity. In the context of complex activities modelling, there is the idea of continuous executions of low-level

activities one after the other, reflecting a specific context in the user's behavior. However, in real-life this approach suffers user's personalization in the sequence of movements and activities that are executed, which also increases the amount of labelling that needs to be done in order for a robust method to be developed. In this paper, the system is called hybrid as it combines data and knowledge-driven approaches that provide scalability to the system, meaning that, it avoids data collection and annotation phases as it requires only some initial activity modelling effort.

There are different approaches to activity recognition that may vary depending on the sensors used, the machine learning algorithms, and the complexity of the activities that are being modeled. Existing work can recognize basic and atomic activities which are performed by a single subject but does not succeed very well to recognize more complex activities which may be combination of atomic ones. Daily life is not only about these simple activities. Blanke & Schiele [55] has discussed this issue in detail and has provided a potential solution for recognition of composite activities. Another issue regarding efficient complex activities recognition is that existing work is based on the assumption that a person will perform only one activity at a time. It can be true for ambulatory activities such as running and walking. But there are many situations in which users are performing concurrent activities i.e., multiple activities at the same time. For example, a person can be reading a newspaper while drinking coffee or having lunch while watching TV. Very little research has been done in this area and there is a potential for further work in this area. Further details about this challenge can be found in [56].

Moreover, present solutions for activity recognition face the issue of variability, meaning that a different person might perform the same activity differently, or the same person could perform the same activity at a different pace. Many existing systems cannot deal with variability problem i.e., if the same activity is performed by a different person, the system's recognition accuracy is very low. In addition, if the same person performs the same activity in a different style, the system's performance degrades. Modern systems should be robust and should deal with the issue of variability. It is still an open issue and needs further research.

One conclusion that can be drawn is that complex activities-behavior recognition is a difficult task mainly because of the uncertainty and complexity of the data collected by the sensors. Most researchers handle this problem by over simplify the experimental setting of their work by assuming that users often carry out single activities one at a time or multiple activities consecutively, one after another, or they focus on a limited group of activities. There is not any robust method or knowledge on how to detect multiple goals in a real-world scenario yet, however there is be given some effort towards understanding human activities context through wearable sensors.

8.1.1 Wearable specific literature

Nowadays smartwatches are becoming increasingly popular and companies adopt plethora of features related with activity tracking and eHealth monitoring. Unlike mobile phones, which might be left on a desk during indoor activities or exercises, a smartwatch often is used for the whole day without ever removing it, ultimately being a tool for real-time monitoring 24/7. The superior portability, the additional embedded sensors, such as Heart Rate Sensor, and the fact that a watch's position does not change drastically in

accordance to human body, have contributed towards the increase of research interest on activity and behavioral tracking using wearables.

Jordao et al. [57] proposed a human activity recognition method that bases on convolutional neural networks (CNN) using handcrafted features of 3D accelerometer signals. To perform the activity recognition task based on sensor data, the authors use the WHARF dataset [A1]. The WHARF dataset involves data that correspond to 14 activities and collected using a device placed on the wrist of each subject. The main idea is to build a simple 3-layer CNN that can extract patterns from accelerometer and time data. The authors use a partition technique to artificially augment the data. Moreover, the wrist roll and pitch orientation angles have been taken into account to provide a better separation between activity classes. The results of this analysis are concatenated to represent the input vector to CNN. Table1 describes the final accuracy results of this method regarding the activity recognition for every activity.

Activity	bt	ch	gb	lb	sd	su	dg	pg	ut	cs	ds	wk
Acc	92.96 %	91.63 %	70.69 %	40.59 %	71.34 %	65.27 %	90.33 %	89.87 %	81.87 %	82.91 %	79.69 %	94.54 %

Table1. Brush own teeth (bt), comb own hair (ch), get up from the bed (gb), lie down on the bed (lb), sit down on a chair (sd), stand up from a chair (su), drink from a glass (dg), pour water into a glass (pg), use the telephone (ut), climb the stairs (cs), descend the stairs (ds) and walking (wk)

Kim et al. [58] studied activity recognition challenges emphasizing on the eating activity using low power smartphone and wrist-wearable sensors that capture data from the subject and the environment. In particular, there are accelerometer, hygrometer, illuminometer and thermometer data. The eating activity could consist of many low-level contexts such as the spatial and the temporal background, the movement of the wrist and temperature. To achieve the task of eating activity recognition, the authors propose a probabilistic method that relies on Bayesian networks. For evaluation purposes, 25 volunteers of various ages performed ten activities [A2] reaching 948 minutes of data. The volunteers asked to perform unique activities at a specific same time, wearing a wrist-wearable device and having a smartphone. Moreover, to collect real-life data, the data collection took place where the volunteers lived. The authors first examined cases where the subject performed eating or non-eating activities (corresponding results at Table2). The results showed that the proposed BN classified better in the non-eating activity than the eating activity.

	Predict Eating activity	Predict Non-eating activity
Eating activities	TP = 136354	FN = 42937
Non-eating activities	FP = 33949	TN = 165773

Table2. Confusion matrix of eating/non-eating activities of the proposed Bayesian Network

Zubair et, al [59] propose a wearable activity recognition framework that uses the best possible minimum features subset. The authors try to explore specific features that will increase the classification accuracy and the computational capability of the wearables. This research employed a dataset which collected using four body-worn tri-axial sensors in four different body positions (waist, left thigh, right ankle and right arm). Moreover, the corresponding dataset contains data acquired during five activities that refer to sitting, sitting down, standing, standing up and walking. The authors proposed a pre-processing by calculating the rotation angles about accelerometer data. A correlation feature-based process was initialized to select useful features for classification. Regarding the classification algorithms, the authors applied two classifiers, Random forest and an ensemble method of a C5.4 decision tree. This research found that Random forest performed with better accuracy. Table3 describes the results of this activity recognition framework. Table 4 presents an overall model evaluation performance using precision and recall metrics.

Activity	sitting	sitting down	standing	standing up	walking
Acc	99.99%	99.38%	99.97%	99.28%	99.94%

Table3. Activity recognition accuracy results using Random forest

Activity	sitting	sitting down	standing	standing up	walking
Precision	99.9%	99.7%	99.9%	99.5%	100%
Recall	100%	99.5%	99.9%	99.5%	100%

Table4. Activity recognition precision and recall results

Peng et, al [60] study a multi-task approach to the activity recognition problem. A multi-task learning-based method is proposed to solve simple and complex activity recognition tasks jointly. The evaluation of this research was established using two public datasets: UbiComp 08 dataset [A3] and Opportunity dataset [A4]. The UbiComp 08 dataset captured using two triaxial accelerometers while the Opportunity dataset was created using five IMUs, two inertial sensors, and 12 acceleration sensors. Both the experimental datasets are widely known for Human activity recognition tasks. The main contribution of this research relies upon the shared structure between simple and complex activities. The authors create a framework with fundamental deep learning schemes such as convolutional neural networks and long-short term memory networks. The CNNs would extract deep features that are relative to HAR tasks thus LSTMs would utilize the temporal context of activity data. By using a CNN and an LSTM network, the authors aim to recognize simple and complex activities jointly. Four complex activities (dinner activities,

commuting, lunch routine, office work) from the UbiComp 08 dataset and five complex activities (relaxing, coffee time, early morning, cleanup, sandwich time) from the Opportunity dataset were selected to evaluate this research. Table 5 shows the confusion matrix of the proposed activity recognition method on classifying complex activities of UbiComp 08 as well as Table 6 shows the corresponding results on classifying complex activities of Opportunity dataset.

	dinner activities	commuting	lunch routine	office work
dinner activities	70.5%	0	6.8%	22.7%
commuting	0	93.8%	3.1%	3.1%
lunch routine	2.5%	0	76.0%	21.5%
office work	0.6%	0	1.1%	98.3%

Table 5. The confusion matrices on classifying complex activities of UbiComp 08 dataset

	relaxing	coffee time	early morning	cleanup	sandwich time
relaxing	91.4%	0	6.9%	1.7%	0
coffee time	0	78.7%	10.2%	1.5%	9.6%
early morning	0.3%	0.9%	95.2%	1.8%	1.8%
cleanup	0	1.0%	7.9%	71.7%	19.4%
sandwich time	0	3.4%	2.6%	3.9%	90.1%

Table 6. The confusion matrices on classifying complex activities of Opportunity dataset

Guan et, al [61] approach the activity recognition task through multiple deep recurrent Long Short Term Memory networks using wearable sensing. This framework validated in popular benchmark datasets such as Opportunity [A4], PAMAP2 [A5] and Skoda[A6] benchmark datasets. All the above-mentioned public datasets involve 3D acceleration data. In particular, Opportunity dataset consists of data captured from body-worn sensors, object sensors and ambient sensors. PAMAP2 and Skoda datasets contain activity data

captured from body-worn sensors. The authors are motivated by improving the robustness of activity recognition systems by developing a HAR framework based on Ensembles of Long Short Term Memory learners. Their work relies on combining multiple deep, recurrent neural networks into a meta classifier. Handling real-world data is challenging since it involves noise in the sensor readings. To tackle this challenge, the authors initialized a modified training procedure for individual LSTM learners, to create various models with a varying view on the training data. Various modified LSTM learners were implemented through a probabilistic selection of subsets of the original data. Table 7 summarizes the results of this research illustrating the performance of every benchmark dataset.

	Opportunity	PAMAP2	SKODA
F1 Score	72.6%	85.4%	92.4%

Table 7. F1 Score of the proposed ensemble LSTM method for each benchmark dataset

Hammerla et, al [62] try to provide an unbiased and systematic exploration of the performance of major deep learning approaches among deep feed-forward networks, convolutional networks and recurrent networks on three different activity recognition benchmark datasets (Opportunity [A4], PAMAP2 [A5], Daphnet Gait dataset [A7]). Each dataset corresponds to an application of HAR. The DNNs aimed to represent a sequence of non-linear transformations to the input data of the network. The CNNs intended to introduce a degree of locality in the patterns matched in the input data and to enable translational invariance. Regarding the RNNs, LSTM cells were employed to exploit the temporal dependencies within the movement data. The authors resulted in models that differ in the spread of recognition performance. Table 8 presents the classification performance for each methodology approach.

	Opportunity	PAMAP2	DG
DNN	88.8%	90.4%	63.3%
CNN	89.4%	93.7%	68.4%
LSTM	90.8%	92.9%	97.3%

Table 8. F1 Score for different datasets that used for activity recognition from multiple classification approaches

Varamin et, al [63] present a novel activity recognition that is based on a deep autoencoder neural network. This research studies the HAR as a prediction problem where the output refers to sets of ongoing activities. The evaluation was established using two well-known public datasets for activity recognition: WISDM [A1] and Opportunity [A4]. This method proposes a solution that involves an unsupervised feature learning step that exploits accessible unlabeled sensor measurements. According to this, a symmetric convolutional auto-encoder was utilized to fine-tune and leverage valuable label information, so as to

extract more discriminative features. Also, for the supervised activity set learning step, the encoder network was augmented with a multi-label classification head and the output layer was adjusted to suit the input. Table 9 presents an overview evaluation performance on the two public datasets where an average of F1 score metric is described.

	WISDM	Opportunity (locomotion)
F1 Score	97.3%	97.3%

Table 9. F1 Score for different datasets that used for activity recognition through autoencoders

8.1.2 Appendix Datasets Overview

WHARF DATASET [A1]	
Toileting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● brush own teeth ● comb own hair
Transferring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● get up from the bed ● lie down on the bed ● sit down on a chair ● stand up from a chair
Feeding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● drink from a glass ● eat with fork and knife ● eat with spoon ● pour water into a glass
Ability to use the phone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● use the telephone
Indoor transportation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● climb the stairs ● descend the stairs ● walk

NoName DATASET for eating activities [A2]	
Activity	Job

washing	undergraduate
walking	graduate
housework	student
eating (dinnerware)	houseworker
eating etc.	no job
conversation	office worker
driving	businessman
sedentary work	
subway	
playing the piano	

UbiComp 08 DATASET [A3]	
Simple Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● unlabeled ● driving bike ● driving cart through supermarket ● driving car ● brushing teeth ● personal hygiene ● kneeling ● running ● sitting having a coffee ● having breakfast ● having dinner ● having lunch ● sitting talking on phone ● using the toilet ● sitting desk activities ● standing talking ● standing having a coffee

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● queuing in line ● standing talking on phone ● standing using the toilet ● walking ● walking while carrying something ● walking freely ● washing dishes ● picking up mensa food ● lying using computer ● wiping the whiteboard ● discussing at whiteboard ● kneeling making fire for barbecue ● fanning barbecue ● washing hands ● setting the table ● watching movie ● making coffee ● attending a presentation ● preparing food ● standing eating
Routines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● unlabeled ● dinner activities ● commuting ● lunch routine ● office work

Opportunity DATASET [A4]	
ADL run	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● groom ● relax ● prepare coffee ● drink coffee ● prepare sandwich ● eat sandwich ● cleanup ● break
Drill run	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● open then close the fridge ● open then close the dishwasher ● open then close 3 drawers (at different heights) ● open then close door 1

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● open then close door 2 ● toggle the lights on then off ● clean the table ● drink while standing ● drink while seated
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PAMAP2 DATASET [A5]	
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● lying ● sitting ● standing ● walking ● running ● cycling ● Nordic walking ● watching TV ● computer work ● car driving ● ascending stairs ● descending stairs ● vacuum cleaning ● ironing ● folding laundry ● house cleaning ● playing soccer ● rope jumping ● other (transient activities)

SKODA DATASET [A6]	
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● write notes ● open engine hood ● close engine hood ● check door gaps ● open door ● close door ● open/close two doors ● check trunk gap ● open/close trunk ● check steering wheel

Daphnet Gait dataset [A7]	
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● write notes● open engine hood● close engine hood● check door gaps● open door● close door● open/close two doors● check trunk gap● open/close trunk● check steering wheel